

DEVELOPMENT OF INCREASED EPITHELIAL PERMEABILITY SYNDROME IN RHEUMATOLOGICAL PATIENTS

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Materials and methods of research

Assessment of the integrity of the intestinal barrier using morphological examination of biopsies of the mucous membrane (CO) of various parts of the gastrointestinal tract with subsequent staining with hematoxylin and eosin, which allows to identify ulcerative defects, erosion of CO, to assess the density of cellular infiltrate and its composition, as well as the degree of atrophy, which can serve as indirect signs of altered permeability. To visualize the distances between epithelial cells and the width of intercellular croscopy. For light microscopy, biopsies of the gastric mucosa, duodenum and colon were fixed in 10-12% formalin solution on a phosphate buffer according to Lilly. Paraffin sections were stained with hematoxylin-eosin. For transmission electron microscopy [TEM], tissue samples were fixed with a 2.5% solution of glutaraldehyde on a phosphate or cacodilate buffer, after dehydration in alcohol - acetone, they were filled with an epono-araldite mixture. Ultrathin sections obtained on the ultratome "ULTRACUT" were contrasted in the Hitachi H-600 electron microscope. For scanning electron microscopy [SEM], the preparations after the above fixation were subjected to dehydration and alcohol-acetone, then dried by the critical point method in the HCP-2 apparatus and sprayed with gold in the IB-2 apparatus. Examined in the Hitachi S405A electron microscope

Photographing was carried out on a color film Kodak Professional Pro Foto 100 or Fuji color superia 100. Micrographs were scanned on a scanner Scan Prisa 640P (Acer) and subjected to computer processing on a computer CompuTek Pentium III Windows 2000. Semi-thin epoxy sections stained with methylene blue fuchsin were also examined light-optically. Light-optical micrographs were obtained using an Axioscope (Zeiss) microscope with a Sony digital camera. Computer processing of microphotographs was carried out on a Pentium-III computer using Microsoft's "Excel-Office" - "Windows-Professional" application programs.

Research results and their discussion

The analysis of the conducted studies revealed significant morphological shifts in all the studied sections of the digestive tract in rheumatological diseases (RH). During the study, rheumatological patients revealed significant changes in the mucous membrane of the duodenum, which are expressed in an increase in infiltration of the stroma of intestinal villi by lymphocytes and plasma cells, expansion of microvessels, an increase in the number of interepithelial lymphocytes, the location of epithelial cell nuclei at different levels, which creates the impression of a false multi-row. The brush border is preserved, as well as the integrity of the epithelial lining of the villi. Most of the goblet cells are emptied. In the interstitial spaces, the contents of various types are determined, among which microorganisms can also be

distinguished. Stroma infiltration also increases in the colon mucosa, and the number of interepithelial lymphocytes increases. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) shows that the microrelief of the surface of the mucous membrane of the pyloric part of the stomach largely loses its regularity. The apical parts of the surface-pit cells are located at different heights. There are intercellular gaps and depressions. On the surface of the cells there is a small layer of various inclusions and overlays. There are also microerosions of the apical parts of epithelial cells [Fig.3]. The villi of the duodenum have a fairly regular leaf-shaped shape with a small number of different inclusions on the surface. Among which it is possible to distinguish erythrocytes, lymphocytes and other formations.

The lumen of the crypts of the colon is filled with mucus, various inclusions, including microorganisms, are located in it [Fig.5]. Smaller erosions are detected on the surface of epithelial cells.

The change in the morphology of the gastrointestinal tract aggravates the use of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs). In the stroma of the mucous membrane of the pyloric part of the stomach, the number of plasma and other infiltrate cells increases. Surface-pit epithelial cells are characterized by pronounced polymorphism. This polymorphism is expressed in different cell height and shape and mucoid content. The number of interepithelial lymphocytes increases [fig.6,7]. The intercellular spaces in the basal parts of the epithelial cells expand significantly, which leads to their extrusion. There are significant areas of eroded epithelial cell surfaces. Significant changes are also noted in the mucous membrane of the duodenum. The number of infiltrate cells increases significantly. At the same time, plasma cells dominate in the stroma of the villi. The basal parts of the enterocytes become enlightened, the intercellular gaps increase. Some enterocytes lose their connection with the basement membrane. However, in the duodenum at the debut of NSAID use, there are no violations of the integrity of the epithelial lining and the formation of microerosions. SEM studies have shown that in the pyloric part of the gastric mucosa, the "debut" of the use of NSAIDs causes significant changes in the microrelief of the surface. The apical parts of the cells become different in shape, size and height [Fig. 10]., which leads to a violation of the rhythm and relative symmetry of the microrelief. Numerous microerosions are detected on the cell surface. The number of overlays on the cell surface increases, the intercellular spaces expand. Morphological studies have shown that the very presence of RB causes significant changes in the pyloric part of the stomach of the duodenum and colon. Before taking NSAIDs, these changes have the character of chronic inflammation, expressed to one degree or another. For the stomach, this picture fits into the framework of chronic gastritis without atrophy. For the duodenum - moderate duodenitis. In the colon, changes occur in the form of moderate colitis. The initial use of NSAIDs causes more pronounced changes in the mucous membrane. In the mucous membrane of the pyloric part of the stomach, there are violations of the connections of the integumentary pit cells with the basement membrane, the expansion of intercellular spaces in the basal part of the epithelium, the appearance of microerosions on the apical surfaces of epithelial cells and their pronounced polymorphism. At the same time, there is an increase in inflammatory changes. Changes in the mucous membrane of the duodenum also indicate an increase in the manifestations of inflammation and a weakening of the strength of the epithelial lining. In the colon, changes under the influence of NSAIDs are expressed to the least extent. According to modern concepts, SIEP and microbiota disturbance are considered as a trigger factor or an important element of

the etiopathogenesis of RH [15]. Published works in which the effect of correction of increased permeability of the gastrointestinal tract and microbiotic disorders on the development and course of RH was studied. Thus, there are data indicating a decrease in the activity of the disease, the level of proinflammatory cytokines and CRP in RA patients with gingivitis after effective sanitation of the oral cavity [16,17]. A number of works are devoted to the effectiveness of probiotics in RA, AS and SLE [18,19,20]. A significant increase in intestinal permeability was found, not only in patients with AS, but also in their closest relatives, which indicates the genetic nature of intestinal permeability disorders leading to the development of SIEP [21], which requires a comprehensive approach to the treatment of patients with this group of diseases, aimed at reducing the severity of autoimmune lesions of the elements of the musculoskeletal system, and to reduce the severity of SIEP.

Conclusion:

Thus, close contacts between epithelial cells and the microbiota play a key role in maintaining the integrity of the intestinal barrier. The pathological permeability of the intestinal barrier leads to the translocation of bacteria and their metabolites into the internal environment of the body, which can cause inflammatory changes in target organs and create a pathophysiological basis for the development of a number of autoimmune diseases, which creates the need for an integrated approach to the diagnosis and therapy of patients with this group of diseases.

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